

**Iran University of Science and Technology
Mechanical Engineering Department**

English Summary of Master's Thesis

**Evaluation of hypoxia and angiogenesis in cancerous tumors
using a droplet-based microfluidic device**

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October 2022

Abstract

Reliable in vitro models are needed to study cancer biology under controlled and reproducible conditions. Conventional two-dimensional cell culture is useful and simple, but it cannot fully represent the structural and biochemical complexity of the tumor microenvironment. Animal models provide more physiological information, but they are expensive, time-consuming, and may not accurately predict human tumor behavior. To address this gap, a droplet-based microfluidic platform was designed, fabricated, and experimentally evaluated for the production of uniform droplets and hydrogel-based microgels suitable for three-dimensional cell culture.

The biological motivation of this work was the future evaluation of tumor hypoxia and angiogenesis. These two processes are strongly related to tumor growth, metastasis, and drug resistance. A cross-flow microfluidic chip was designed in CATIA and fabricated using soft photolithography and PDMS replica molding. Initial experiments were performed with deionized water as the dispersed phase and oil phases containing Span 80 as the continuous phase. The influence of capillary number, flow-rate ratio, and oil type on droplet diameter, generation frequency, and droplet spacing was investigated.

The platform was then adapted for calcium-alginate microgel production using sodium alginate and Ca-EDTA in the dispersed phase, followed by stabilization in a calcium chloride bath. Spherical and highly uniform microgels were produced, with reported coefficients of variation below 5%. Preliminary HEK-293 cell encapsulation was also demonstrated. Overall, this work established a practical microfluidic route for generating cell-compatible alginate microgels as a foundation for future cancer-on-chip and tumor microenvironment studies.

Keywords: Biomedical microfluidics; droplet microfluidics; cancer-on-a-chip; tumor microenvironment; alginate microgels; cell encapsulation; soft photolithography; hypoxia; angiogenesis; three-dimensional cell culture

Executive Summary

This Master's research focused on the development of a droplet-based microfluidic platform for producing uniform droplets, calcium-alginate microgels, and preliminary cell-laden microgels. The work was motivated by the need for improved in vitro systems that can support future studies of tumor hypoxia and angiogenesis in a three-dimensional microenvironment.

The main engineering contribution was the design and fabrication of a cross-flow microfluidic chip with a widened post-junction channel and a spiral downstream section. The geometry was selected to support controlled droplet breakup, improve droplet uniformity, and increase residence time for gelation-related processes.

The experimental work was completed in three main stages. First, water-in-oil droplet generation was studied using paraffin oil and Span 80. The effects of capillary number and flow-rate ratio on droplet diameter, droplet generation frequency, and droplet spacing were evaluated. Second, different continuous phases, including paraffin oil, mineral oil, and olive oil, were compared to understand the role of oil properties in droplet formation. Third, the platform was adapted to generate calcium-alginate microgels by using an internal gelation strategy based on sodium alginate and Ca-EDTA.

A key practical challenge was premature gelation and channel blockage. This was addressed by replacing direct calcium chloride gelation inside the chip with a controlled Ca-EDTA and acid-triggered gelation method, followed by off-chip calcium chloride stabilization. This approach enabled the production of spherical and highly monodisperse alginate microgels. The reported microgel size distributions showed coefficients of variation below 5%, confirming good reproducibility and size control.

As a final step, HEK-293 cells were encapsulated inside alginate microgels. This experiment demonstrated the feasibility of producing cell-laden microgels using the developed platform. Direct quantitative biological assays of hypoxia and angiogenesis were not completed in the reported stage of the work. Therefore, the main outcome should be understood as the development and validation of an engineering platform for future tumor microenvironment studies.

1. Background and Motivation

Cancer remains one of the most serious health challenges worldwide. Tumor development is not controlled only by the genetic behavior of cancer cells. It is also strongly influenced by the local tumor microenvironment, including cell-cell interactions, cell-matrix interactions, oxygen transport, nutrient availability, pH, mechanical properties, and interstitial pressure. These factors can affect tumor growth, metastasis, and response to therapy.

Among the many features of the tumor microenvironment, hypoxia and angiogenesis are particularly important. Hypoxia occurs when oxygen delivery becomes insufficient inside a growing tumor mass. This condition can appear because tumor cells proliferate rapidly and oxygen cannot diffuse efficiently into the inner region of the tissue. In response, angiogenesis may be activated, allowing the formation of new blood vessels to improve oxygen and nutrient

supply. These processes are directly related to tumor progression and are also connected to drug resistance and metastasis.

A major difficulty in cancer research is the lack of simple and reliable experimental models that can reproduce these microenvironmental conditions. Two-dimensional cell culture remains widely used because it is simple, inexpensive, and easy to control. However, cells grown on flat surfaces do not experience the same spatial organization, mechanical support, and transport gradients that exist in real tissues. As a result, two-dimensional models often fail to reproduce the behavior of solid tumors.

Animal models provide more complex biological responses, but they have several limitations. They are costly, time-consuming, and affected by physiological differences between animals and humans. Ethical concerns also motivate the development of alternative in vitro systems. For these reasons, three-dimensional cell culture systems and microfluidic organ-on-chip technologies have become important tools in biomedical research.

Microfluidics provides precise control over small volumes of fluids inside microscale channels. This makes it possible to generate uniform droplets, control transport phenomena, and create small three-dimensional environments for cell culture. Droplet-based microfluidics is especially useful because it can produce highly uniform droplets or microgels at high throughput. When hydrogels are used, the droplets can be converted into three-dimensional scaffolds that support cell encapsulation and culture.

Hydrogels were selected in this work because they can mimic some features of the extracellular matrix. They contain a large amount of water, can be formed under mild conditions, and can provide a three-dimensional environment for cells. Calcium alginate was selected as the main hydrogel material because it is biocompatible, easy to gel, and widely used for cell encapsulation. The final goal was to establish a microfluidic platform that could support future cancer-on-chip studies by producing uniform cell-laden microgels.

2. Research Objectives

The main objective was to design, fabricate, and experimentally evaluate a droplet-based microfluidic device for producing uniform droplets and alginate microgels suitable for three-dimensional cell culture.

The specific objectives were:

- To design a cross-flow microfluidic chip capable of generating uniform droplets from two immiscible phases.
- To fabricate the device using soft photolithography and PDMS-based microfabrication.
- To assemble an experimental setup based on syringe pumps, microscopy, and image recording.
- To study the influence of capillary number and flow-rate ratio on droplet size, generation frequency, and droplet spacing.
- To compare different continuous oil phases and evaluate their effect on droplet formation.

- To produce calcium-alginate microgels using a controlled internal gelation method.
- To wash and stabilize the generated microgels for possible biological use.
- To demonstrate preliminary cell encapsulation inside alginate microgels.
- To establish a technical foundation for future studies of tumor hypoxia and angiogenesis in cancer-on-chip systems.

3. Methodology

3.1. Microfluidic Device Design and Fabrication

A cross-flow microfluidic configuration was selected for droplet generation. In this geometry, the dispersed phase enters the main channel and is sheared by the continuous phase at the junction. This configuration was selected because it is simple, reproducible, and suitable for producing droplets with controlled size.

The device was designed using CATIA V5R20. The chip included two inlets and one outlet. One inlet was used for the dispersed phase, and the other was used for the continuous phase. The channel width at the droplet generation junction was 120 μm . After the junction, the channel was suddenly expanded to 200 μm and then gradually widened to 400 μm with an approximate slope of 3° . A spiral downstream section with four turns was also included to increase the residence time of droplets inside the chip. This design feature was important for later gelation experiments, where more time was needed before the generated droplets exited the device.

Figure 1. Schematic of the designed cross-flow microfluidic chip showing the dispersed-phase inlet, continuous-phase inlet, droplet generation junction, widened post-junction channel, spiral residence section, and outlet. (COMSOL simulation)

As shown in Figure 1, the chip geometry was designed to combine controlled droplet formation at the junction with a longer downstream residence path. This design allowed droplet formation to be observed near the junction while also providing additional channel length for stabilization during gelation-related experiments.

The device was fabricated using soft photolithography. A silicon wafer was used as the substrate for mold fabrication. SU-8 2100 negative photoresist was spin-coated to create a mold with a height of approximately 200 μm . After soft baking, the coated wafer was exposed to ultraviolet light through a printed mask prepared from the CATIA design. The pattern was then developed and hard-baked to create the final SU-8 mold.

PDMS was poured over the mold, degassed under vacuum, and cured at 65 °C. After curing, the PDMS layer was peeled from the mold, inlet and outlet holes were punched, and the PDMS structure was bonded to a glass slide using plasma bonding. The bonded device was then heat-treated to improve bonding stability. Since droplet generation required hydrophobic channel walls, Aqualap treatment was applied to the channels.

Figure 2. Soft photolithography and PDMS fabrication workflow used to produce the droplet-based microfluidic chip, including SU-8 mold preparation, UV exposure, PDMS casting, bonding, and final chip preparation.

The fabrication process shown in Figure 2 provided a reproducible route for producing transparent PDMS microfluidic devices. Transparency was important because droplet formation, movement, and microgel generation needed to be monitored by optical microscopy.

3.2. Flow framework and experimental setup

Droplet generation was analyzed using dimensionless numbers commonly applied in microfluidics. The most important parameter was the capillary number, which compares viscous forces to interfacial tension forces. Under microfluidic conditions, the Reynolds number is usually low, so the flow is dominated by viscous and surface tension effects rather than inertia. The Bond number is also very small at the microscale, so gravity effects are usually negligible.

The capillary number was used to describe the relationship between flow conditions and droplet formation. In general, increasing the capillary number increases the effect of viscous shear from the continuous phase. This can change the droplet breakup process and influence droplet diameter, formation frequency, and spacing.

The experimental setup included a dual-channel syringe pump, syringes, microtubes, the fabricated microfluidic chip, and an optical imaging system. The syringe pump enabled independent control of the dispersed-phase and continuous-phase flow rates. The imaging system was used to record droplet formation at the junction and to measure droplet characteristics downstream.

Figure 3. Experimental setup for droplet generation and optical characterization, including syringe pump, microfluidic chip, microscope/camera system, and enlarged views of droplet formation inside the channel.

The setup shown in Figure 3 allowed the flow rates of both phases to be controlled precisely. This was essential because the main experimental variables were the continuous-phase flow rate, the dispersed-phase flow rate, the flow-rate ratio, and the resulting capillary number.

3.3. Droplet generation protocols

The first experimental stage focused on water-in-oil droplet generation. Deionized water was used as the dispersed phase, and paraffin oil containing 1 vol% Span 80 was used as the continuous phase. Span 80 was added as a surfactant to stabilize the droplets and reduce coalescence.

The continuous-phase flow rate was varied from 0.06 to 1.2 mL/h. The flow-rate ratio, defined as Q_d/Q_c , was varied from 0.125 to 1. The corresponding capillary number ranged from approximately 0.0018 to 0.036. Under these conditions, droplet diameter, droplet generation frequency, droplet spacing, and flow behavior were evaluated.

A second set of experiments was performed to compare different oils as continuous phases. Paraffin oil, mineral oil, and olive oil were tested under comparable flow conditions. Deionized water was again used as the dispersed phase, and Span 80 was added to the oil phase. This comparison was performed to evaluate how the properties of the continuous phase affected

droplet generation. The same general trend with capillary number and flow-rate ratio was observed for the three oils, but droplet size, generation frequency, and spacing were affected by the oil properties.

3.4. Alginate gelation, washing, and cell encapsulation

After the droplet generation behavior was characterized, the platform was adapted for calcium-alginate microgel formation. Sodium alginate was selected because it can form hydrogels under mild conditions and is suitable for cell encapsulation. In the gelation stage, the dispersed phase contained 2 wt/vol% sodium alginate and 1 wt/vol% Ca-EDTA in deionized water. The continuous phase contained paraffin oil, 3 wt/vol% Span 80, and 0.5 vol/vol% acetic acid.

Direct gelation with calcium chloride inside the microfluidic channel was first considered, but this approach caused premature gel formation and channel blockage. To solve this problem, Ca-EDTA was used as a delayed calcium source. Under acidic conditions, calcium ions are released more gradually, which allows gelation to begin inside the droplet while reducing the risk of immediate blockage. After leaving the chip, the droplets were collected in a 4 wt/vol% calcium chloride bath to complete stabilization.

Figure 4. Calcium-alginate microgel formation and collection strategy, showing on-chip droplet generation, acid-triggered internal gelation using Ca-EDTA, off-chip stabilization in calcium chloride solution, and washing of produced microgels.

As shown in Figure 4, the gelation strategy combined controlled on-chip droplet generation with off-chip calcium chloride stabilization. After collection, the microgels were centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 3 minutes, washed two to three times, and transferred into well plates. This washing process was necessary to remove the oil phase and acidic components before biological use.

For preliminary cell encapsulation, HEK-293 cells were cultured in DMEM supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum and 1% penicillin-streptomycin. The cells were maintained at 37 °C and 5% CO₂. Before encapsulation, cells were trypsinized, counted, centrifuged, and mixed with the alginate/Ca-EDTA dispersed phase. The same microfluidic and downstream stabilization approach was then used to produce cell-laden alginate microgels.

4. Main Results and Contributions

The first main result was the successful generation of droplets using the designed cross-flow microfluidic device. In the paraffin oil experiments, a clear relationship was observed between capillary number, flow-rate ratio, droplet size, frequency, and spacing. At a fixed flow-rate ratio, increasing the capillary number reduced the droplet diameter. This occurred because stronger shear from the continuous phase promoted earlier breakup of the dispersed phase.

At the same time, increasing the capillary number increased droplet generation frequency and reduced the distance between consecutive droplets. At a fixed capillary number, increasing the dispersed-to-continuous flow-rate ratio produced larger droplets because more dispersed phase entered the junction before breakup. However, when the flow-rate ratio approached 1 at higher capillary numbers, droplet spacing became very small and stable breakup became more difficult.

Figure 5. Droplet diameter as a function of capillary number at different flow-rate ratios during water-in-oil droplet generation with paraffin oil as the continuous phase.

The relationship shown in Figure 5 confirms that droplet size can be controlled through the capillary number and flow-rate ratio. This was an important result because controllable droplet generation is required before uniform microgels can be produced.

The second main result was obtained from the comparison of paraffin oil, mineral oil, and olive oil. The overall trend of droplet formation remained similar for the three oils. However, droplet size and generation frequency changed because each oil had different physical properties. Under comparable conditions, mineral oil produced larger droplets and larger droplet spacing, while olive oil produced smaller droplets and higher generation frequency. Paraffin oil was finally selected as the most suitable continuous phase for later microgel experiments because it provided favorable droplet uniformity and practical handling.

Figure 6. Comparison of droplet formation in olive oil, paraffin oil, and mineral oil at different flow-rate ratios, showing the effect of continuous-phase properties on droplet size, spacing, and generation behavior.

As presented in Figure 6, the continuous phase had a clear influence on droplet morphology and spacing. This comparison supported the selection of paraffin oil for the next stage of calcium-alginate microgel production.

The third and most important result was the successful generation of calcium-alginate microgels. The produced microgels were spherical, uniform, and suitable in size for cell encapsulation and three-dimensional culture. The size distribution data showed that the generated microgels had coefficients of variation below 5%. In several conditions, the CV values were close to or below 2%, indicating strong monodispersity.

(a) $Q = 0.1$

(b) $Q = 0.3$

(c) $Q = 0.05$

Figure 7. Size distributions and optical microscopy images of calcium-alginate microgels produced at different flow-rate ratios and capillary numbers, showing spherical morphology and high monodispersity.

The results shown in Figure 7 demonstrate that the platform can generate microgels with controlled size distribution. This is important for biological applications because microgel size affects diffusion, nutrient transport, oxygen availability, and cell-cell interaction. Highly variable microgel size would make biological experiments less reproducible. Therefore, the observed monodispersity was one of the strongest outcomes of the work.

Scanning electron microscopy was also performed to evaluate the surface and internal structure of dried alginate microgels. The SEM images showed a porous microstructure after fixation, dehydration, drying, and coating. This porous structure is important because it can support nutrient transport, molecular diffusion, and cell communication when the microgels are used as scaffolds.

Figure 8. SEM images of calcium-alginate microgels after fixation, dehydration, drying, and gold coating, showing spherical morphology and porous microstructure.

As shown in Figure 8, the microgels maintained an approximately spherical structure after sample preparation. The visible porous morphology supports the potential use of alginate microgels as three-dimensional scaffolds for cell culture.

The final experimental contribution was the preliminary encapsulation of HEK-293 cells inside alginate microgels. Microscopy images confirmed that cells could be introduced into the alginate/Ca-EDTA dispersed phase and encapsulated during microgel formation. This result provided proof of feasibility for producing cell-laden microgels with the developed platform.

Figure 9. Microscopy images of HEK-293 cell-laden alginate microgels, demonstrating preliminary cell encapsulation using the developed droplet-based microfluidic platform.

The cell-laden microgels shown in Figure 9 represent the bridge between the engineering part of the work and future biological studies. Although direct quantitative assays of hypoxia and angiogenesis were not completed, the platform created a practical basis for future experiments. Future studies can use cancer cells, endothelial cells, oxygen-sensitive markers, HIF-1 α expression, VEGF quantification, or endothelial network formation assays to directly evaluate hypoxia and angiogenesis inside controlled three-dimensional microgel environments.

Overall, the main contributions can be summarized as follows:

- A cross-flow droplet-based microfluidic chip was designed and fabricated.
- Droplet generation was experimentally characterized under different flow conditions.
- The effects of capillary number, flow-rate ratio, and oil type were evaluated.
- A practical internal gelation method was developed for calcium-alginate microgel production.
- Spherical and highly monodisperse microgels were produced.
- Preliminary cell encapsulation was demonstrated.
- A foundation was established for future cancer-on-chip studies related to tumor hypoxia and angiogenesis.

5. Publications and Conclusion

5.1. Publications Related to This Work

The experimental and computational work developed during and after this Master's research contributed to the following publications:

- Performance optimization of droplet formation and breakup within a microfluidic device – Numerical and experimental evaluation
International Journal of Heat and Fluid Flow, Elsevier, 2024.
- A simple yet effective microfluidic device for the in-situ formation of uniform-sized cell-laden microgels
Biomedical Physics & Engineering Express, IOP Publishing, 2026.
- Numerical simulation of calcium alginate microgel formation and particle encapsulation by in-situ internal gelation method
Journal of Bioscience and Bioengineering, Under review.

These publications are directly connected to the design, fabrication, droplet generation, microgel formation, and cell encapsulation aspects of the work. They also show the continuation of the research direction toward biomedical microfluidics, computational modeling, and cell-laden microgel systems.

5.2. Conclusion

A droplet-based microfluidic platform was developed for the controlled production of droplets, calcium-alginate microgels, and preliminary cell-laden microgels. The work was motivated by the need for improved three-dimensional in vitro models that can support future studies of the tumor microenvironment, especially hypoxia and angiogenesis.

The designed cross-flow chip successfully generated droplets under controlled flow conditions. The effects of capillary number and flow-rate ratio were systematically evaluated, and the results showed that droplet size, frequency, and spacing could be controlled by adjusting the flow parameters. The comparison of paraffin, mineral, and olive oils also showed that the continuous phase plays an important role in droplet formation behavior.

The transition from simple droplets to calcium-alginate microgels was a key step. Premature gelation and channel blockage were addressed by using Ca-EDTA and acid-triggered internal gelation, followed by external stabilization in calcium chloride. This strategy enabled the production of spherical and highly monodisperse alginate microgels. The low coefficients of variation confirmed the reproducibility of the platform and its suitability for microscale cell culture applications.

Preliminary HEK-293 cell encapsulation further demonstrated the potential of the system for generating cell-laden microgels. Although full biological validation of tumor hypoxia and angiogenesis was not completed, the engineering foundation was successfully established. The platform can be further developed by using cancer cells, endothelial cells, controlled oxygen gradients, biological markers, and quantitative assays.

This work provided practical experience in microfluidic device design, soft photolithography, PDMS fabrication, droplet generation, hydrogel microgel production, microscopy-based analysis, and cell encapsulation. It also created a strong foundation for future research in biomedical microfluidics, cancer-on-chip systems, organ-on-chip platforms, and personalized medicine.